

POLITICAL SCIENCE

Review

Vol. 14. No. 2, 2026

Published by:
Department of Political Science,
Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Ilorin, Ilorin Nigeria.

POLITICAL SCIENCE REVIEW

Vol. 14. No. 2, 2026

**A PUBLICATION OF THE DEPARTMENT OF POLITICAL
SCIENCE, FACULTY OF SOCIAL SCIENCES, UNIVERSITY
OF ILORIN, ILORIN NIGERIA**

E- ISSN 3121-9330

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For further information, contact: The Editor, PSR, Department of Political Science, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of florin. +2348030675617 OR: The Managing Editor +2347064275374.

NOTES ON CONTRIBUTORS

Moshood Olayinka Salahu (PhD) is with the Department of Politics and Governance, Kwara State University, Malete, Nigeria

Amin Amin (PhD) is of the Department of Public Administration, Kwara State Polytechnic, Ilorin, Nigeria

Ember Yange works with the Department of Political science and International Relations, Nile University of Nigeria Abuja

Mubarak Muhammad Usman currently lectures at the Department of Political science and International Relations, Nile University of Nigeria Abuja.

Nathaniel Temini Jesu Okunade (Ph,D) is a lecturer with the Department of Public and International Law, Faculty of Law, Alhikma University Ilorin, Kwara State

Olubukola Olufunke Temi -Okunade is a Graduate Student in the Department of Public Law, Faculty of Law, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Kwara State

Faniran Sunday Oladele is of the Department of Public Administration The Oke-Ogun Polytechnic, Saki

Adedokun Mosaudu Kunle is a staff of the Department of Local Government Studies The Oke-Ogun Polytechnic, Saki

Olabisi Hakeem Olalekan is with the Department of Public Administration The Oke-Ogun Polytechnic, Saki

Ibraheem Saheed Adesina is lecturer in the Department of Public Administration The Oke-Ogun Polytechnic, Saki

Quazeem Abdrosheed Ajedokun lectures in the Department of Public Administration The Oke-Ogun Polytechnic, Saki

Abdullahi, Abdusalam Arije is a lecturer in Centre For Peace and Security Studies Al-Hikmah University Ilorin, Nigeria.

Dr. S. A. RAJI is with the Centre For Peace And Strategic Studies, University of Ilorin, Nigeria

Solomon Ayantayo Ojo is a lecturer with the Department of Political Science and International Relations, KolaDaisi University, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria
Muhammed Babatunde Usman is a Postgraduate student in the Department of Political Science, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria.

Ibraheem, A. Kolapo is a researcher in Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin-Nigeria
Ibrahim, I. Yahya (PhD) is a lecturer in the Department of Political Science, Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin-Nigeria

Taiwo Ogundele is of the Centre for Peace Studies and Security Studies, Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin

Enabunene Osazee Israel (PhD) lectures in the Department of Public Administration.
University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria.

Imuentiyan Osayomwanbor Sophia (PhD), is a lecturer in the Department of Public Administration, Edo State Polytechnic, Usen.

Ayodele, A. is with the Centre for Peace and Security Studies, Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin, Nigeria.

Shittu, R. is of the Centre for Peace and Security Studies, Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin, Nigeria

Ekundayo, J.K. is of the Centre for Peace and Strategic Studies, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.

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The Role of Traditional Institutions in Mediating Communal Conflicts: Evidence from Ilorin Emirate, Kwara State, Nigeria

Abdullahi, Abdusalam Arije

*Centre For Peace and Security Studies Al-Hikmah University Ilorin,
Nigeria.*

arijeabdullahiabdulsalam@gmail.com

Dr. S. A. Raji

*Centre for Peace and Strategic Studies,
University of Ilorin, Nigeria*

adray2010@yahoo.com

Abstract

Communal conflicts pose persistent threats to peace and development in diverse societies, particularly in post-colonial African contexts where state-centric approaches often lack local legitimacy. While formal institutions struggle with accessibility and trust, traditional authorities, rooted in cultural norms, offer culturally resonant mechanisms for mediation and reconciliation. This study examines the contributions of traditional institutions to managing communal conflicts in Ilorin, the multi-ethnic emirate capital of Kwara State, Nigeria. Drawing on a descripto-explanatory design, purposive sampling, semi-structured interviews with 30 stakeholders (including 20 traditional rulers), Likert-scale questionnaires, thematic analysis, and triangulation with secondary sources and media reports, the research investigates conflict drivers, security impacts, and the roles/challenges of traditional actors. Findings reveal land disputes and political competition as primary triggers (means >4.17), with significant effects on economic disruption,

property destruction, and resource strain. Traditional rulers, led by the Emir, wield strong moral authority (mean 4.43), accessibility, and trust, often surpassing formal systems, through consensus-based mediation, elder involvement, and reconciliation practices. However, modernization, political interference, and resource constraints pose challenges. The study underscores the enduring relevance of traditional institutions in hybrid peacebuilding and recommends constitutional recognition, capacity-building, inclusive reforms (e.g., youth/women involvement), and state-traditional collaboration. These insights contribute to debates on indigenous mechanisms in conflict transformation and offer policy pathways for sustainable peace in Nigeria's pluralistic settings.

Keywords: traditional institutions, communal conflict, conflict resolution, Ilorin Nigeria, peacebuilding, hybrid governance, traditional rulers, mediation

Introduction

Peace, safety, and security are essential for the development and achievement of a good quality of life in any human society. According to the Chinese, conflict presents an opportunity for change (National Open University of Nigeria, 2010). Conflicts often emerge from incompatible goals among opposing parties. Additionally, conflict reflects a state of disharmony within the international system (National Open University of Nigeria, 2010). While conflicts are inevitable, they are also a normal and integral part of human life. They can arise at various levels international, (sub)regional, community, organizational, and among states or ethnic groups. However, no conflict is entirely free from political undertones, as many stems from struggles over control of the political landscape within communities across the globe, which together form our interconnected world (Albert, 2007). Communal conflicts frequently occur as a result of inter-group tensions and the manipulation of religious sentiments, often fuelled by political elites

pursuing their selfish interests (Orji, 2014). Communal conflicts are not only peculiar to Nigeria. Among the countries in which these conflicts have existed all over the world are: in Africa; conflicts have existed in Nigeria, Sudan, Kenya, Ethiopia, and Democratic Republic of Congo (International Crisis Group, 2018); in Asia; India, Myanmar, Pakistan, Indonesia, and Sri Lanka (South, 2008); in Europe; Bosnia-Herzegovina, Ukraine, Russia, Belgium, and Northern Ireland (Ware & Kisriev, 2010); in North America; United States, Guatemala, Canada, Mexico and Honduras (Alexander, 2012); in South America; Brazil, Peru, Colombia, Bolivia, and Venezuela (Almeida, 2019); in Oceania; Papua New Guinea, Fiji, Solomon Island, Indonesia, and Australia (MacLeod, 2011). Traditional institutions for conflict resolution have long existed in African societies, playing a vital role in promoting peace and fostering harmony (National Open University of Nigeria, 2010). These institutions spanned various spheres, including political structures such as the family and palace, economic settings like markets, social organizations such as age-grade groups and professional associations, and religious systems involving deities, ancestors, and sanctuaries. According to Abdulmalik (2010), in a pluralistic society like Nigeria, conflicts are more frequently linked to social, communal, religious, or ethnic tensions than to other causes. Even political conflicts are often interpreted through the lens of religious or ethnic divisions.

Best (2012) argues that in all civilized societies, there is an increasing reliance on peaceful traditional methods to settle disputes. The image of violence portrayed by the media does not accurately reflect the dominant approach to resolving conflicts. There is a significant amount of traditional peace and non-violent conflict resolution happening at various levels in communities worldwide, much of which is either misrepresented or overlooked by the media (Terepyschyi & Khomenko, 2019). A wide range of non-violent traditional conflict management methods exist within the field of conflict transformation, available at individual, family, group, community, and international

levels. These methods can be classified into two categories (Ajayi & Buhari, 2014). The first, proactive methods, aim to prevent conflicts from arising in the first place. Examples include undocumented community-based trust-building, communication, good governance, and inter-party collaboration. The second, reactive methods, address conflicts that have already emerged or are escalating. These include third-party interventions such as mediation, brokerage, conciliation, arbitration, and litigation.

Communal conflict remains one of the most pervasive threats to peace and development in many societies globally, often driven by competition over land, identity, resources, and power. According to the United Nations (2020), over 80% of violent conflicts worldwide occur within states rather than between them, with local communities frequently embroiled in disputes that can escalate into broader crises. While formal state mechanisms and international actors have long focused on peacebuilding and conflict resolution, there is growing recognition of the importance of local, culturally grounded approaches, including traditional institutions, in managing and mitigating communal conflicts (Zartman, 2000; Lederach, 1995).

In Africa, communal conflicts have been particularly pronounced due to colonial-era boundaries, ethnic diversity, resource scarcity, and socio-economic inequalities (Boone, 2012; Young, 1994). The continent has witnessed numerous instances where state-centric models of conflict management have struggled to address local grievances effectively. As a result, scholars and practitioners have increasingly turned to traditional authorities chiefs, councils of elders, religious leaders as credible actors in peace processes (Osaghae, 2000; Uwazie, 2011). These institutions, often predating colonial states, possess legitimacy rooted in cultural norms and localized dispute-resolution practices that emphasize consensus and reconciliation (Boege, 2006).

In Nigeria, communal conflicts have posed persistent challenges to national unity, security, and development. The country's extraordinary

ethnic and religious diversity, combined with pressures over land, chieftaincy succession, and political representation, has generated frequent inter-group tensions (Egwu, 1998; Adediran, 2021). While formal legal systems and security agencies play critical roles in conflict management, they have often been criticized for their inadequacy, bias, or lack of legitimacy at the local level (Albert, 2017). Consequently, traditional institutions remain vital, especially in rural and peri-urban settings, where they mediate disputes, enforce customary law, and maintain social order (Ajayi & Buhari, 2014).

Ilorin, the capital of Kwara State in Nigeria's North-Central region, presents a compelling context for examining the role of traditional institutions in managing communal conflict. Historically, a frontier emirate with a unique blend of Yoruba and Fulani heritage, Ilorin's traditional system is headed by the Emir and supported by hierarchical chieftaincy structures (Adeyemi, 1976; Salau, 2018). The city and its environs have experienced periodic communal tensions over land ownership, chieftaincy succession, and ethnic identity (Jimoh, 2014). Yet, traditional authorities have often played central roles in mediating these disputes and preventing escalation.

Despite the recognized importance of traditional institutions in conflict management, there remains limited empirical research specifically focused on their roles, strategies, and effectiveness in Ilorin. This study, therefore, seeks to examine how traditional institutions in Ilorin, Kwara State, contribute to the management of communal conflict, exploring their historical legitimacy, mechanisms of mediation, and contemporary challenges in a rapidly modernizing society.

Literature Review

This section is done based on the following sub-sections:

Conflict:

According to Bell (2021), human existence is inherently marked by struggle and disagreement, often arising from competition over

resources, differing values, power dynamics, and inequalities in social justice. Such tensions reflect an incompatibility of goals and interests which, if not properly managed, can escalate into more serious conflict. Jeong (2008) argues that our survival on this planet depends on how effectively we manage the various dimensions of conflict driven not only by clashing interests and values, but also by underlying hostilities. No society is entirely free from conflict; the two are fundamentally intertwined. While conflict is often perceived as negative, it also has a constructive side. When handled properly, it can lead to self-discovery, mutual understanding, personal growth, and societal development benefits that would be unattainable in its absence.

Okpaga (2002) views conflict as often emerging from the pursuit of wealth, power, influence, and prestige. Similarly, Mmuya and Maunde (2002) define conflict as a confrontation or lack of agreement between two or more parties within an organization or group. Taken together, conflict can be understood as a disagreement, controversy, or clash of ideas and perspectives upheld by individuals or groups, which may ultimately damage previously harmonious relationships. When conflict arises, it has the potential to lead to both positive and negative changes whether in governance, socio-economic structures, or grassroots communities.

In the same vein, Bamikole (2008) describes conflict as arising from divergent interests among people or groups, which may be rooted in material, religious, ethnic, or ideological differences, among other causes. However, Albert (2001) offers a more nuanced perspective, arguing that conflict is not inherently negative. Rather, he sees it as a vital mechanism through which individuals and groups express their goals and aspirations. He further asserts that conflict can serve as a pathway to creative problem-solving and the development of a shared identity.

From these scholarly perspectives, it is clear that conflict does not occur in a vacuum; it emerges from interactions between people with differing

interests. While often viewed negatively, conflict can also be a catalyst for change and progress, revealing previously hidden solutions and driving development in unexpected ways.

Traditional Rulers:

According to Baldwin (2016), the significance of traditional leadership in African societies cannot be overstated. While it is well known that traditional authorities no longer hold official roles in the political or governance structures of Nigeria, they continue to function in an unofficial capacity as consultative bodies to local, state, and federal governments.

In the same vein, Okonkwo et al. (2019), sees a traditional ruler as an individual divinely selected or chosen by the people of a community through a careful selection process to govern its social, economic, and political affairs. This role can also be viewed as one inherited from birth, coming from a royal lineage, and carrying the responsibility of leadership, which is passed down through generations. Traditional rulers are often individuals or groups with the necessary background, knowledge, and wisdom to understand and address issues as they arise. Various scholars have defined traditional rulers based on the specific time and circumstances in which they operate.

Cookey (2010) defines a traditional ruler as an individual who, by virtue of their ancestral position, occupies the throne or stool of a particular area. This person is appointed according to the customs and traditions of the community, and their position predates the arrival of the British in Nigeria. According to this definition, traditional rulers hold executive, legislative, and judicial powers. Examples of leaders fitting this description include the Emirs in Northern Nigeria, such as the Emir of Bauchi, Kano, Zaria, Adamawa, Ilorin, and Gombe. In Western Nigeria, notable figures include the Alaafin of Oyo, the Ooni of Ife, and the Oba of Benin. In contrast, Eastern Nigeria had a different system of administration before colonial rule, with small communities

governed through a mix of democratic processes and hereditary leadership.

Abu (2017) views traditional rulers as individuals who claim royal heritage, being descendants of the founders of dynasties in their specific regions. This lineage grants them respect from the people within their territories. In contrast, I would define a traditional ruler as someone who is not only of royal descent but also skillful, competent, articulate, and civilized. Such rulers are empowered by traditional principles and possess the intellectual capacity to effectively manage and resolve conflicts.

Theoretical Framework

The following theories are applied. These are:

Human Needs Theory:

The main assumption of this theory is that all human has basic human needs which they seek to fulfil and that the denial and frustration of these needs by other groups or individuals could affect them immediately or later, thereby leading to conflict (Rosati et al. 1990). 'Basic human needs' in this sense comprise physical, psychological, social and spiritual needs. In essence, to provide access to one (e.g. food) and deny or hinder access to another (e.g. freedom of worship) will amount to denial and could make people resort to violence to protect these needs.

Needs theorists over time have identified some of these needs, the deprivation of which causes conflict. Maslow in his *Motivation and Personality* identified physiological needs, safety needs, belongingness and love, esteem and self-actualization. Burton lists response, stimulation, security, recognition, distributive justice, meaning, need to appear rational and develop rationality, need for sense of control and the need for a role defense (Burton, 1979:72). He refers to some needs as basic, such as food, shelter, sex and reproduction, etc. Edward Azar names some basic needs like security, distinctive identity, social

recognition of identity and effective participation in the processes that shape such identities (Azar, 1994).

Burton identified a link between frustration, which forces humans into acts of aggression and the need on the part of such individuals to satisfy their basic needs. According to him, individuals cannot be taught to accept practices that destroy their identity and other goals that are attached to their needs and, because of this, are forced to react against the factors, groups and institutions that they see as being responsible for threatening such needs.

Human needs for survival, protection, affection, understanding, participation, creativity, and identity are shared by all people, are irrepressible, and, according to Burton, have components (needs for recognition, identity, security, autonomy, and bonding with others) that are not easy to give up. No matter how much a political or social system tries to frustrate or suppress these needs, it will either fail or cause far more damage in the long run. Like Gurr's thesis on relative deprivation, Max Neef (1991) believes that the tension between deprivation and potential are main issue addressed by the human needs theory because when important needs are not sufficiently satisfied, economic and political problems will continue to grow. The absence of economic opportunities, hyper-inflation, and penury are manifestations of economic imbalance, while political imbalance leads to fear, xenophobia (intense fear or dislike of foreign people, their customs and culture), crime and violence, forced migration, voluntary or forced exile and political marginalisation. All these constitute the root cause of bitter conflicts.

Even though scholars identify a wide range of human needs, some of which they consider to be basic human needs, they agree on the fact that the frustration of these needs hampers the actualisation of the potential of groups and individuals, subsequently leading to conflict. Secondly, there is a near consensus among them that to resolve a conflict situation, or to prevent it from occurring, the needs have to be met with

appropriate satisfiers, those things that were denied them in the first instance.

Relational Theory:

Relational theory attempts to provide explanations for violent conflicts between groups by exploring sociological, political, economic and historical relationships between such groups. Thus, the belief here is that cultural and value differences, as well as group interests, all influence relationships between individuals and groups in different ways. At the sociological level, differences between cultural values are a challenge to individual or group identity formation processes and create the tendency to see others as intruders who have to be prevented from encroaching upon established cultural boundaries.

Political economy, for example, identifies power and the advantages that it confers as a key source of tension between different interest groups within a political system. In situations where multiple groups share a common resource that is fixed in nature, the chances that each will attempt to eliminate, neutralize or injure the other, or monopolise such a resource (Maoz, 1982) is as high as the tendency to enter into a negative relationship.

Methodology

Research Design:

This study is constructed as a hybrid of descripto-explanatory studies and inductive interpretation via thematic analysis, which aids in capturing the study's normative dimensions. According to Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2009), when a research study uses description, it is more likely to be a forerunner to explanation; descripto-explanatory investigations are the result. According to the preceding viewpoint, descriptive research is a means to an end rather than an end in itself. As a result, the study uses a descripto-explanatory approach throughout the analyses and inductive interpretation to draw inferences from data based on ideas synthesized. On the one hand, the descripto-explanatory

process was not only seen as an extension of exploratory research, but it also involved examining, recording, evaluating, and interpreting events in order to gain a better understanding of current and future trends. In fact, descriptive research aims to "provide an accurate profile of people, events, or situations." The inductive approach, on the other hand, is non-experimental and aids in the grouping and understanding of variables as well as the production of generalizations, principles, or theories with universal validity (Creswell, 2014; Hennink, 2007; Johnson, 2015; Katz, 2015).

Population of the Study:

In every research, the most crucial item to the researcher is the population of the study. As a result, the complete collection of live and inanimate objects under research is referred to as the population of studies. Biereenu-Nnabugwu (2006), referenced in Aleyomi (2017), defines population as not just the number of individuals being examined, but also institutions, items, objects, or members of the target being studied or observed, based on this definition. As a result, population can be thought of as the total group of individuals, events, or items of interest that a researcher wants to look at.

As a result, the study's demographic includes bureaucrats, legislators, and members of the general public. A total of 30 people were picked at random from the public, with 20 traditional rulers (district heads, drawn from within and outside the Emir's palace) and 10 civil servants making up the sample.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique:

It is impossible to obtain absolutely precise data from any group, and Smith (2004) correctly states that the major objective of sampling is to effectively maintain and decrease the time and expense that would have been utilized if the entire population was researched. Similarly, Johnson (2015), Marshall, and Rossman (2014) assert that sampling is important when the overall population is big, when the project's time is restricted,

and when the project's resources (human and material) are insufficient. However, as previously said, the study population is huge, and there are insufficient human and material resources to cover the entire population. As a result, the researcher limits the sample size of the study to largely reports from newspaper editions and literature from experts in the field, research institutes, and policy formulators. As a result, the major representative members are recruited from both State and Non-State entities, reducing costs and ensuring the study's early conclusion.

As a result, we used tables to explain the data from the reports. According to the findings, the four Nigerian newspapers, Vanguard, Punch, ThisDay, and The Nation, published various reports on the concerns, including editorials, news pieces, and letters to the editor. Furthermore, the researcher uses purposive sampling as a sample technique in order to generate data for this study. It's impossible to use all of the samples that are representative of the population under investigation (Gray, 2013). As a result, the study uses tiny samples of persons, cases, and phenomena nested within the framework of Nigeria's communal strife. According to Tongco (2007), the usage of purposive sampling approach is dependent on the study's purpose, and it is strongly recommended for use if the study's goal is to gather ideas, good insights, and critical appraisal experience. Another reason to employ purposive sampling rather than random sampling is the dynamic nature of data in qualitative methods, as opposed to quantitative methods, which are planned and pre-prepared. In other words, unlike random sampling, qualitative sampling samples can change during fieldwork and do not need to be pre-planned. As a result, this shows that the respondents were chosen with some flexibility. The decision to consult a participant may evolve into a decision to select another informant, which the researcher may not have chosen initially.

Instrument of Data Collection:

Primary data was employed in this study since it allows the researcher to gather or obtain information directly from the respondents. The interview was created based on the literature analysis and designed to capture respondents' background information as well as data relevant to the study's aims. To acquire information from respondents, this study used structural questions that were self-administered. The decision to utilize a questionnaire was based on the idea that data acquired by a questionnaire was simple to comprehend and seen as authoritative. Questionnaires gave researchers more control over the research process.

There were two portions to the questionnaire that were used. The first section included questions on the respondent's and their organization's demographic information. The second segment of the report focused on Nigeria's intra-party conflicts and democracy process. The study employed structure questions and Likert type questions with scale of 1 to 4 where 1 - Strongly Disagree; 2 - Disagree; 3 - Agree; 4 - Strongly Agree (Zira, Ogbu & Ojo, 2017). The respondents had to read, comprehend, and select a suitable option. The researcher gave the questionnaires to the respondents in person with the support of research assistants to guarantee that the information received from the respondents was clear and to improve the response rate.

However, apart from the fact that it is the minimal criterion for qualitative research, the high cost of logistics, time constraints, and the global pandemic later limit selection of members to five and individual stakeholders. Unprocessed data from government departments and agencies makes up the other primary sources. Because of the 'raw' nature of data collecting, primary data sources are extremely dependable in social research (Babbie, 2007; McNabb, 2015). However, there is a good chance that participants may misrepresent facts. To avoid this problem, the researcher investigated all of the sources (fieldwork and literature), including raw data from official gazettes, using data triangulation principles and intensive-research procedures.

The primary source also aided in the reconciliation of data acquired from governmental agencies and other sources, which informed the study's results and conclusions. As one of the data gathering instruments, the study uses both semi-structured and unstructured interviews. The rationale for the semi-structured interview was that certain key informants complained about time constraints and inevitable logistics in meeting with them one-on-one. Secondary sources of information for this project included literature and document reviews, as well as library materials such as books, journal articles, published official gazettes, national dailies, published and unpublished materials such as theses and monographs, as well as materials obtained from the internet. Secondary data aided in improving the validity of research findings and reducing the likelihood of bias from primary sources. The documents were obtained from the University of Ilorin as well as the Ilorin National Library.

Method of Data Presentation and Analysis:

The process of dividing a large amount of data into smaller component parts in order to disclose the meaning, observable aspects, nature, and structure of the data is known as data analysis (Creswell, 2014; Gilbert, 2006; Gray, 2013). Data analysis, according to Blaikie (2003), is the process of reviewing and treating data collected in order to answer the study question (s). As a result, the study used theme analysis to examine the data that had been gathered qualitatively. In addition, theme and direct quotations were used as interview analysis tools. Data was collected and examined frequently through 'immersion' in order to uncover developing patterns, themes, and sub-themes. This allows the researcher to organize the information into sections.

Thematic analysis concludes data, which is usually text, by systematically and objectively identifying particular classified qualities for themes or sub-themes within it (Wray, Markovic & Manderson, 2007). Descripto-explanatory and inductive interpretation were used in the study. The descriptive and explanatory approaches lay the

groundwork for analysis, while inductive interpretation assists in explaining, comprehending, and gaining insights in order to obtain a generally acceptable conclusion.

The use of thematic analysis in this study is significant for a variety of reasons, including the following. One, it is simple, time-saving, cost-effective, and versatile, since it eliminates the need for expensive surveys to be designed and sent. Two, it enables for the use of existing material as the basis for data, such as high-powered committee reports, unpublished government gazettes, memoranda, memoire, or electronic mails (Gray,2013).

As a result, three separate tools were used in the research to apply the triangulation technique (primary source, secondary source, and unprocessed official materials). These various tools assisted in validating the efficacy of the data acquired. Triangulation, according to Golafshani (2003) and Gray (2013), is an authoritative and scientific technique in research design, particularly qualitative research design, that helps to validate several collected data by using cross-confirmation, thereby increasing the credibility and defensibility of results. Indeed, the triangulation principle refers to the employment of many techniques in the same study to collect data in order to check the validity and robustness of any conclusions. As a result, the researcher will use the statistical instrument to answer the questions posed for this study project (Mean and Standard Deviation).

Findings and Discussion of the Study

Demographic Profile of Respondents

Table 4.1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristic	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1. Age	25-35 years	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Restricted access to e-service • Low citizen participation and inclusion • High dropout rates during service delivery • Digital divide deepens
	36-45 years	8	
	46-55 years	10	
	56 years and above	6	
Gender	Male	24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced uptake of e-government platforms • Vulnerability to misinformation and cyber threats
	Female	6	
		20.0	
2. Educational Level	Primary	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low public trust and security • Hinder innovation and investment
	Secondary	8	
	Tertiary	66.6	
3. Ethnic Group	1-5 years	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low public trust and security
	6-10 years	7	
	11+ years	63.4	
4. Religious Affiliation	Yoruba	15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Islam • Christianity • Traditional Religion
	Hausa-Fulani	10	
	Others	5	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The demographic profile shows that 80% of respondents were male, reflecting the male-dominated nature of traditional authority structures in Ilorin. The majority (63.4%) have lived in Ilorin for over 11 years, indicating substantial local knowledge and experience. The religious composition (73.3% Muslim, 23.3% Christian) mirrors Ilorin's predominantly Islamic character while acknowledging its religious diversity.

Research Question 1: What is the nature of communal conflicts in Ilorin metropolis?

Table 4.2: Nature of Communal Conflicts in Ilorin

Statement	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev
Conflicts in Ilorin are mostly religious	8 (26.7%)	12 (40.0%)	4 (13.3%)	4 (13.3%)	2 (6.7%)	3.67	1.18
Conflicts are mostly ethnic in nature	6 (20.0%)	14 (46.7%)	5 (16.7%)	3 (10.0%)	2 (6.7%)	3.63	1.07
Land disputes are a major source of conflict	12 (40.0%)	15 (50.0%)	2 (6.7%)	1 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	4.27	0.78
Political competition fuels communal tensions	10 (33.3%)	16 (53.3%)	3 (10.0%)	1 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	4.17	0.75
Statement	10 (33.3%)	16 (53.3%)	3 (10.0%)	1 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	4.17	0.75
Statement	10	24	6	13.33	2.02	3.67	1.18
Age	24	14	24	16.73	3.33	3.63	1.07
Gender	6	14	46.7	5 16.7	3 10.0	2.67	1.07
Statement	63.3%	20.0%	5 (16.7%)	3 (6.7%)	0 (0.0%)	4.27	0.78

Source: Field Survey, 2025 Note: SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, N = Neutral, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree

The analysis reveals that land disputes emerge as the most significant source of communal conflict in Ilorin (Mean = 4.27, Std. Dev = 0.78), followed by political competition (Mean = 4.17, Std. Dev = 0.75). This finding aligns with Albert (2001) and Egwu's (2016) assertion that land conflicts are Nigeria's main cause of intercommunal violence. Religious conflicts (Mean = 3.67) and ethnic tensions (Mean = 3.63) also feature prominently, reflecting Ilorin's complex multi-ethnic and multi-religious composition.

Interview Evidence: A traditional ruler interviewed stated:

"Most conflicts we handle today stem from boundary disputes between farming communities and grazing areas. The pressure on land has increased with population growth and climate change pushing herders southward." (District Head, Ilorin East, Personal Interview, 2024).

Research Question 2: What are the effects of communal conflict on internal security in Ilorin metropolis?

Statement	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev.
Conflicts disrupt economic activities	14 (46.7%)	13 (43.3%)	2 (6.7%)	1 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	4.33	0.76
Property destruction occurs during conflicts	11 (36.7%)	16 (53.3%)	2 (6.7%)	1 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	4.23	0.73
Conflicts lead to population displacement	9 (30.0%)	15 (50.0%)	4 (13.3%)	2 (6.7%)	0 (0.0%)	4.03	0.85
Loss of lives occurs in major conflicts	7 (23.3%)	12 (40.0%)	6 (20.0%)	4 (13.3%)	1 (3.3%)	3.67	1.09
Conflicts strain government resources	13 (43.3%)	14 (46.7%)	2 (6.7%)	1 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	3.67	1.09
	13 (43.3%)	14 (46.7%)	2 (6.7%)	1 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	4.30	0.75

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The analysis demonstrates that communal conflicts significantly impact internal security in Ilorin. Economic disruption emerges as the most severe effect (Mean = 4.33), followed by strain on government resources (Mean = 4.30) and property destruction (Mean = 4.23). This supports Otite and Albert's (2004) observation about the significant loss of lives and property resulting from communal conflicts in Nigeria.

Case Study Analysis: The 1997 Erin-Ile and Offa boundary dispute, as documented by Akinnusi, Alao, and Mavalla (2019), illustrates these security implications. The conflict resulted in:

- i. Disruption of trade routes between the communities
- ii. Destruction of farmlands and market infrastructure
- iii. Temporary displacement of over 500 families
- iv. Deployment of additional security forces, straining state resources

Research Question 3: What are the roles played by traditional rulers in fostering peace in Ilorin metropolis, and what challenges do they face?

Statement	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev.
The Emir and local chiefs have moral authority to settle conflicts	16 (53.3%)	12 (40.0%)	1 (3.3%)	1 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	4.43	0.73
Traditional methods are still relevant today	14 (46.7%)	13 (43.3%)	2 (6.7%)	1 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	4.33	0.76
Traditional rulers are accessible during disputes	12 (40.0%)	15 (50.0%)	2 (6.7%)	1 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	4.27	0.74
Elders and religious leaders play supporting roles	11 (36.7%)	16 (53.3%)	2 (6.7%)	1 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	4.23	0.73
Traditional institutions are more trusted than formal systems	10 (33.3%)	14 (46.7%)	4 (13.3%)	2 (6.7%)	0 (0.0%)	4.07	0.87

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Recommendations for Strengthening Traditional Institutions in Conflict Resolution

Drawing from the research findings on the enduring role of traditional institutions in Nigerian peace-building, the following recommendations are proposed. These are tailored to specific stakeholder groups, emphasizing practical, collaborative, and sustainable pathways toward hybrid governance that respects cultural heritage while addressing modern challenges.

For Government (Federal, State, and Local):

Governments at all levels should move decisively to accord traditional institutions the constitutional and legal recognition they deserve. This begins with formalizing their role in conflict resolution through targeted constitutional amendments or comprehensive legislation that clearly delineates jurisdictional boundaries between traditional and formal legal

systems, thereby minimizing overlaps and authority disputes. Equally important is the creation of robust legal frameworks that enable collaborative mechanisms, allowing both systems to work in tandem during disputes.

Financially, governments should treat traditional peace-building as a public good by establishing dedicated budget lines for these initiatives, creating accessible conflict resolution funds that traditional institutions can draw upon for emergency interventions and reconciliation programs, and investing in basic infrastructure, such as dignified court venues and meeting halls, that dignify the process and signal state respect. Capacity building must be systematic: regular training programs should introduce traditional leaders to contemporary mediation techniques, human rights standards, and procedural justice, while structured knowledge-exchange platforms with security agencies foster trust and coordination. Standard operating procedures for joint action during crises would further streamline collaboration.

Finally, political non-interference is non-negotiable. Clear protocols, backed by independent oversight bodies, should shield traditional processes from partisan manipulation, and succession processes must prioritize merit and community legitimacy over political patronage.

For Traditional Institutions Themselves:

Traditional institutions must embrace thoughtful modernization without sacrificing authenticity. Opening meaningful spaces for women and youth, through advisory councils or dedicated committees would enrich decision-making and ensure intergenerational legitimacy. Methods should evolve to tackle new forms of conflict, cyber-induced disputes, resource struggles intensified by climate change, or identity-based tensions, while remaining rooted in cultural principles. Formal documentation of rulings, precedents, and agreements would enhance transparency, accountability, and institutional memory.

Coordination with state actors should be institutionalized through memoranda of understanding with police, judiciary, and local governments, joint conflict resolution committees, and regular inter-institutional consultations. Traditional leaders should also invest in peer-learning networks across Nigeria's diverse ethnic landscape. On prevention, community-based early warning networks, proactive peace education, and conflict-sensitive development projects that tackle root causes (land inequity, unemployment, ethnic marginalization) offer the greatest long-term impact. Finally, leaders should actively seek professional training in mediation and negotiation and develop cultural competency programs tailored to Nigeria's multi-ethnic, multi-religious reality.

For Civil Society Organizations:

Civil society has a vital advocacy and bridge-building role. Organizations should campaign vigorously for constitutional recognition and legal safeguards for traditional institutions, while offering technical assistance and training support. Documenting and widely disseminating success stories, how a palace intervention averted communal violence or reconciled warring communities, can shift public and elite perception from scepticism to appreciation.

CSOs are uniquely positioned to convene difficult dialogues between traditional and formal systems, support multi-stakeholder peace programs, and run public awareness campaigns that highlight the cost-effectiveness and restorative power of indigenous approaches. Ongoing research remains essential: rigorous studies on effectiveness, innovation, and adaptation, paired with accessible repositories of best practices, will provide evidence for policy reform and replication elsewhere.

For Development Partners and International Organizations:

Development partners should prioritize funding for capacity-building, hybrid governance pilots, and documentation of indigenous practices.

Technical assistance can usefully share global lessons on modernizing traditional authority (from Rwanda's gacaca evolution to South Africa's recognition of customary courts) and support policy design for sustainable integration. Creating platforms, regional summits, South-South exchanges, and practitioner networks, would allow African traditional leaders to learn from one another and amplify their voices internationally.

For Academic Institutions:

Universities and research centres should elevate the study of traditional institutions from the margins to the mainstream scholarship. Interdisciplinary programs merging anthropology, political science, law, and peace studies, combined with ethical partnerships directly with traditional institutions, would generate culturally grounded knowledge. Curricula should incorporate indigenous governance and conflict resolution modules, while executive education programs serve sitting leaders and mediators. Research priorities must include hybrid governance models, the integration of digital tools into early warning and community engagement, and comparative economic analyses that quantify the fiscal advantages of traditional versus purely formal systems. Producing policy briefs, open-access case studies, and teaching materials will ensure that academic work translates into real-world impact.

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